

Synthesis of 1-Aryl-2-mercapto-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thiones and their Addition Products with α,β -Unsaturated Carbonyl Compounds and Aryl Cyanamides as Antithyroidal Agent

R. PRASAD and P. K. SRIVASTAVA*

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 11 September 1991, revised 25 June 1992, accepted 3 July 1992

Different 1-aryl-2-mercapto-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thiones have been synthesised by the dealkylation of 1-aryl-2-benzylmercapto-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione with thiourea and HCl. These mercapto triazine when treated with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds and aryl cyanamides gave the corresponding addition products and tested for their antithyroidal activity.

With the intention of synthesising compounds which would modify antithyroid thiols so as to reduce their toxicity and improve their activity¹, addition of 1-aryl-2-mercapto-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thiones (2) with various α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds and aryl cyanamides were taken up. This type of addition may favourably influence absorption, transport, distribution, localisation and toxicity as well as stability².

Mercaptotriazine (2) was obtained by dealkylating³ 1-aryl-2-benzylmercapto-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (1) by refluxing it with thiourea and concentrated HCl in ethanol (Scheme 1). The precursor was obtained by known methods⁴. Mercaptotriazine (2) when refluxed with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds in ethyl acetate, afforded the addition product (3). A cold solution of 2 in acetone when mixed with a solution of aryl cyanamide hydrochloride⁵ in acetone gave *N*-aryl-*S*-(1-aryl-4-phenyl-6-thioxo-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)isothiuronium hydrochloride (4). These compounds could not be crystallised without decomposition and hence purification was achieved by repeated washing with acetone and petroleum ether. Satisfactory elemental analysis, nmr, ir spectral data and chemical behaviour of compounds confirmed their structures.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by using a Thomas-Hoover stirred liquid apparatus and are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were obtained on a JEOL FX 90Q Fourier transform spectrometer (¹H) with Me₄Si as an internal standard and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer.

The aryl cyanamide hydrochlorides were prepared by the reported method⁵. 1-Aryl-2-benzylmercapto-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (1) were prepared⁴ from benzoyl isothiocyanate and *S*-benzyl-*N*-aryl isothiouria.

1-(4-Bromophenyl)-2-mercapto-4-phenyl-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazine-6-thione (2a): Alcoholic solution of 1 (4.66 g, 10 mmol) was mixed with alcoholic solution of thiourea (0.76 g, 10 mmol) and then concentrated HCl (0.8 ml) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2.5 h, then cooled and poured in excess of water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from alcohol as yellow shining crystals (2a; Ar=4-BrC₆H₄; 66%), m.p. 278° (Found: C, 48.53; H, 2.45; N, 11.33; S, 17.19. C₁₅H₁₀N₃S₂Br calcd.: C, 47.87; H, 2.66; N, 11.17; S, 17.02%); $\nu_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 2 610 (SH), 1 635 (C=N) and 1 090 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.72 (1H, s, SH) and 7.33–8.26 (9H, m, ArH); 2b (Ar=2-CH₃OC₆H₄), m.p. 199°; 2c (Ar=4-CH₃OC₆H₄), 205°; 2d (Ar=4-CH₃C₆H₄), 254°; 2e (Ar=4-ClC₆H₄), 262°; 2f (Ar=C₆H₅), 212°. All the compounds (yield 50–70%) gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

S-[1-(4-Bromophenyl)-4-phenyl-6-thioxo-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl]mercaptosuccinic acid (3a): A solution of 2a (3.76 g, 10 mmol) and maleic acid (1.76 g, 15 mmol) in 100 ml of ethyl acetate was refluxed for 4 h and then cooled overnight. Some fumaric acid separated which was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated. A paste thus obtained was washed with benzene, ether and petroleum ether and then recrystallised from alcohol, (60%), m.p. 235° (Found: C, 46.19; H, 2.98; N, 8.71; S, 13.23. C₁₈H₁₄N₃O₄S₂Br calcd.: C, 46.34; H, 2.84; N, 8.53; S, 13.01%); $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3 550–3 300 (COOH), 1 705 (C=O), 1 625 (C=N) and 1 110 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (CDCl₃) 2.19–2.53 (3H, m, CH-CH₂), 7.00–7.83 (9H, m, ArH) and 10.42–10.71 (2H, b, COOH).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were obtained (yield 50–63%) (Table I).

N-Phenyl-S-[1-(4-bromophenyl)-4-phenyl-6-thioxo-1,6-dihydro-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl]isothiuronium hydrochloride (4a): A cold solution of 2a (1.88 g, 5 mmol) in

Ar = 4-BrC₆H₄, 2-CH₃OC₆H₄, 4-CH₃OC₆H₄, 4-CH₃C₆H₄, C₆H₅

Scheme

acetone was mixed with ice-cold solution of phenyl cyanamide hydrochloride (0.77 g, 5 mmol) in acetone (5 ml) with constant stirring for ~ 1 h, the granular white isothiuronium salt separated was filtered and purified by washing it with dry acetone

and ether, (60%) m.p. 242–44° (Found : C, 49.80; H, 3.07; N, 13.37; S, 12.31. C₂₂H₁₇N₂S₂BrCl calcd. : C, 49.76; H, 3.20; N, 13.19; S, 12.06%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 390 (NH), 1 640 (C=N), 1 525 (thio-uriedo linkage) and 1 095 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTITHYROIDAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a—1*

Compd. no.	Ar	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	M.p. °C	Antithyroidal activity**
3a	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	COOH	H	COOH	H	235	1.03
b	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOH	H	282	1.22
c	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	H	H	H	COOH	196	0.89
d	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	CHO	255	1.66
e	2-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	COOH	H	COOH	H	145	1.01
f	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOH	H	225	0.96
g	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	H	H	COOH	236	0.99
h	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	CHO	242	1.07
i	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	COOH	H	COOH	H	190	0.91
j	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	H	COOH	H	249	1.12
k	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	H	H	COOH	210	1.13
l	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	H	H	CHO	262	0.97

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. **Standard thiouracil=1.00.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANTITHYROIDAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4a—o*

Compd. no.	Ar	Ar'	M.p. °C	Antithyroidal activity**
4a	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	242—44	1.08
b	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	283—85	1.19
c	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	235—38	1.34
d	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	198—200	1.15
e	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	170—73	0.96
f	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	145—47	0.88
g	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	180—82	0.99
h	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	161—64	1.09
i	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	> 320	0.91
j	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	215—18	0.89
k	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	160—61	0.94
l	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	163—66	1.12
m	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	185—87	1.14
n	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	154—56	1.03
o	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	246—49	0.81

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. **Standard thiouracil=1.00.

Similarly, other compounds of the series were obtained (yield 50—75%) (Table 2).

Antithyroidal activity: Antithyroidal activity was evaluated by the reported method⁶ in albino rats. Thiouracil was used as standard drug and the compound were taken equimolar to thiouracil.

Appreciable antithyroidal activity was observed in compounds 3a, b, d, e, h, j, k and 4a-d, h, l, m, n (Tables 1 and 2).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, for facilities.

References

1. I. MEVIGH and W. S. HANLEY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 995; L. FIELD and Y. H. KHIM, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 312; U. K. TIWARI, P. K. SRIVASTAVA and V. K. VERMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, 66, 241; L. FIELD and P. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, 16, 428.
2. N. J. HARPER, *Prog. Drugs Res.*, 1962, 4, 221; *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1959, 1, 467.
3. V. K. VERMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 50.
4. M. ELMER and T. B. JOHNSON, *Am. Chem. J.*, 1903, 30, 169; J. GOERDELER and J. NEUFFER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1967, 29, 2791; G. V. NAIR, Ph.D. Thesis, Banaras Hindu University, 1965; R. CHANDRA and P. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1983, 28, 278.
5. H. KRALL and R. H. SAHSTRABUDHEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 345.
6. R. W. RAWSON, D. A. MCGINTY, M. PRISCILLA, M. WILSON and H. LOCKHARD, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1948, 93, 240.